

Graphene Coated Textile Dielectric Materials effect on Performance of Textile Triboelectric Nanogenerator

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Abstract

In the advanced era of smart textiles, numerous textile-based sensors are operating to monitor human well-being. For the continuous working of these sensors an uninterpreted power supply is crucial. Human body motion is a constant and abundant source of biomechanical energy which could be useful to harvest energy for many wearable devices. The triboelectric nanogenerator gained tremendous attention for energy harvesting in wearable devices based on high output power. The performance of triboelectric depends on the surface charge density of triboelectric material. To improve triboelectric performance, numerous methods have been utilized including the surface functionalization and modification in dielectric composition of triboelectric materials as well. The surface charge density is proportional to the relative permittivity of the triboelectric material; hence, the surface charge density can be improved remarkably by enhancing the dielectric value of triboelectric materials. In this work, a vertical contact separation mode nanogenerator is developed on textiles. The top and bottom electrodes were printed on textile with silver paste by screen printing method. The dimensions of printed electrodes were 2.5cm by 5cm. The graphene nanoplatelets coated cotton, polyester, cotton-polyester textiles were applied as the dielectric layer. The coating was done by dip coating method. The surface morphology of printed and coated textiles was analyzed by 3D optical profilometer. The dimensions of the textile dielectric layers were also equal to the electrodes' dimensions. The change in DC output voltage of nanogenerators was observed with the change in graphene nanoplatelets coated textiles. The recorded value of instantaneous output voltage was 0.46V, 0.26V and 0.13V for the combination of graphene nanoplatelets coated polyester-cotton/cotton, polyester and polyester-cotton/polyester textiles respectively. It was also observed that the pure cotton has higher porosity as compared to the polymeric textile. This finding also showed the effect of porosity on the functionality of nanogenerator. Our research focused the simple approach to increase the functionality of the nanogenerators by using graphene nanoplatelets coated textiles of different materials. In the future we will focus in detail on design, porosity and nanomaterials to enhance the output voltage of triboelectric nanogenerator which could be an advantage for energy harvesting at large scale. The textile comfortability and compatibility with human skin can make textile based nanogenerators a promising application in wearable smart electronics, smart sensors, internet of things, wireless communication, and biomedical fields.